

Vibrational mode analysis studies on the configuration and structure stability for the subcarbonyl $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$)

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Abstract : The structure properties and vibrational mode for the transition metal subcarbonyl complex $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$) have been examined by using HF, B3LYP, B3P86, and MP2 methods at 6-311G basis set level. Results indicate that the interaction between Fe and CO should be characterized as a dative bond, in which the synapic basin of the carbon plays the role of the disynapic basin connecting the metal core to the carbon atom. It shows that $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$) species have two states, namely triplet ($^3\Sigma$) and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) states. In line with a recent experimental work, the ground state of FeCO is the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state, but we find that the two states of FeCO are very close in energy at different computational levels, and they are both belonging to $C_{\infty v}$ point group. For $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2$ species, the two states ($^3\Sigma$ and $^5\Sigma$ states) have linear structures ($D_{\infty h}$ point group), and v-type structures (C_{2v} point group). According to the analysis of the data, the ground state is the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state with v-type structure. In $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ species, both the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state have similar energies, and they both have pyramidal structures with C_{3v} point group. The $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$ species have a square (D_{4h} point group) structure in triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state and a cube (T_d point group) structure in quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state, and the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ species have a D_{3h} structure in triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state and a C_{4v} structure in quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state, respectively. Detailed bonding analysis has implied that it is quite possible for the existence of the polycarbonyl Fe with more COs, which will also be possible for other similar transition metal carbonyl complexes. Because CO is a very strong donor-acceptor ligand and transition metals have the *d*-orbitals, it is quite possible for polycarbonyl Fe to exist. Thus further studies are very necessary.

Keywords : Fe, carbonyl compounds, density functional theory, vibrational mode, configuration, structure stability.

Introduction

Carbon monoxide has always been used as a tool to probe transition metal atoms and small clusters adsorbed to support as potential or model catalysts¹. A great amount of efforts have been put into reproducing molecular spectroscopy by quantum chemical calculations based on *ab initio* methods over the past three decades. The metal carbonyls are well-studied and understood². For neutral metal carbonyls, such as $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$, $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$ and $\text{Cr}(\text{CO})_6$ and so on, the vibrational frequencies of $\gamma(\text{CO})$ in different metal carbonyls are considerably lower than the value of free CO (2143 cm^{-1}). The carbonyl group acts as an electron acceptor from *d*-block metals though π back-donation. So in many industrial processes metal carbonyls are employed as catalysts for hydroformylation and

the Fischer-Tropsch synthesis of acetic acid³.

In respect of their importance in industry and biological processes, many investigations have been paid attention to the interaction of carbon suboxides with functional biological and material molecules. There have been extensive studies (both experimental⁴⁻¹⁷ and theoretical¹⁸⁻³²) on small transition metal carbonyls. However, the interaction details and their nature are still undiscovered completely. Therefore, detailed investigation concerning the configuration and structure stability of the transition metal subcarbonyls is very necessary.

Recently, the elucidation of reaction mechanisms via vibrational mode of analysis has got more attentions. The changes of the vibrational frequencies and vibrational

modes must be relative to the transformation of the structures³³.

A recent survey of the stretching frequencies of CO bounded to biological molecules has shown that there is an obvious change in the vibrational frequency of CO³⁴, and the affecting factors resulting in the frequency shift mainly involve the ligand substituents³⁵, CO ligand binding geometry and steric effects³⁶⁻³⁸, redox potentials³⁹, CO binding affinities⁴⁰ and charge and polar interactions in the protein pocket^{41,42}. To interpret the dependence of the CO binding on these factors, many interesting models have been established. Oscar González-Blanco and Vicenc Branchadella studied the Fe-CO bond dissociation energies of Fe(CO)₅ using density functional theory in 1998⁴³, but the stability of different states and the vibrational modes have not been studied so far. Compared with the studies on transition-metal carbonyl complexes, the studies on the vibrational modes and structure stability have been appeared to be absent. Obviously, the continuously increasing attention to these studies about the irregular bonding interaction has indicated that it is very important to explore these kinds of slight-weakly bound systems for the investigations of the interaction between CO and the nonmetal-centered active sites in biological and large molecules⁴⁴.

The difficulties in assigning the numerous observed bands in a spectrum to particular vibrational modes have also been largely overcome with the aid of theoretically determined normal coordinates⁴⁵. For a number of small molecules, highly correlated wave functions employing basis sets of medium size can produce estimates of vibrational frequencies within an average deviation of about 1% from the experimental values⁴⁶. However, the quantitative predictions of vibrational intensities have turned out particularly difficult. The quantum mechanical evaluation of vibrational intensities in the infrared spectra has been discussed in a number of comprehensive studies and reviews. The primary emphasis of the review is to such as giving a detailed theoretical investigation on the geometric parameters, dissociation energies, harmonic frequencies, vibrational modes, and other relevant properties of Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) species to interpret the nature of the interaction between CO and the transition-metal.

Methods of Calculation :

All the optimizations on Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) species at the triplet and quintet states have been carried out using

the hybrid density functional theory (DFT) and the second-order Moller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) methods at an extensive 6-311G basis set level. The corresponding three density functional theory (DFT) methods are composed of the exchange correlation functions of Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP), Lee *et al.*, Perdew (B3P86) and Hartree-Fock (HF), respectively.

In recent years, it is remarkable that DFT has been used as a reliable and computationally inexpensive method which is capable of successfully predicting the properties of difficult systems. To confirm the calculated results, the geometries which have first been optimized using DFT method are reoptimized by the second-order Moller-Plesset perturbational theory, and the harmonic vibrational frequencies are also calculated via finite differences of analytic gradients using MP2 method. DFT has been proved to be an effective method for the study of electronic structures and vibration properties of molecular complexes. All molecular geometries were fully optimized by using 6-311G basis set at B3LYP. At the same level of the theory, the infrared spectra including vibrational frequencies, vibrational mode and IR intensities were obtained via analytic second derivative methods in order to determine the nature of different stationary points. The total energy was also calculated. The interaction energy for the Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) complexes was considered as difference between the total energy of the complexes and the separated molecules at the infinite distance. At 298.15° the zero-point vibration energy (ZPE) correction and the thermal correction (TC) were calculated at the B3LYP/6-311+G* level. The calculation of single-point energy was done by using the unrestricted coupled cluster method including single and double excitation and including perturbation estimates of the effects connected with triple excitation (CCSD(T)), which has been shown to predict energies more reliably^{47,48} than other different methods.

The calculations were primarily confined for the configuration, structure stability, vibrational frequencies and vibrational mode to analyses Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) species at the triplet and quintet states. All of the calculations were performed by using the program GAUSSIAN 98.

Results and discussion

Table 1 and Fig. 1 give the sum of electronic and zero-point energies obtained using three DFT (HF, B3LYP and B3P86) methods and the second-order Moller-Plesset

Table 1. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/particle) and calculated bonding energies for the stable configurations (Hartree/particle)

System	FeCO	Fe(CO) ₂	Fe(CO) ₃	Fe(CO) ₄	Fe(CO) ₅
HF (³ Σ)	-1374.9373	-1487.4611	-1600.3274	-1713.0781	-1829.8893
HF (⁵ Σ)	-1374.9320	-1487.6751	-1600.2412	-1713.0331	-1829.9558
B3LYP (³ Σ)	-1376.9777	-1490.3828	-1603.7174	-1717.1211	-1829.9996
B3LYP (⁵ Σ)	-1376.9595	-1490.3913	-1603.6646	-1717.0753	-1830.1934
B3P86 (³ Σ)	-1377.7654	-1491.3688	-1605.0314	-1718.4625	-1832.1736
B3P86 (⁵ Σ)	-1377.7514	-1491.4126	-1604.9933	-1718.4076	-1832.2179
MP2 (³ Σ)	-1375.5322	-1488.0565	-1601.0934	-1716.6950	-1829.9996
MP2 (⁵ Σ)	-1375.3177	-1488.1097	-1601.0874	-1716.6857	-1829.9996
Bonding energy	-0.344	-0.6098	-0.9116	-1.1812	-1.21
1/n bonding energy	-0.344	-0.3049	-0.3039	-0.2953	-0.242

Fig. 1. Configurations of Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) molecules.

perturbational theory (MP2) with a relatively large basis set (6-311G) for Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) molecules at their triplet (³Σ) and quintet (⁵Σ) states, respectively. The calculated bonding energy of every stable configuration is also shown in Table 1. As we can see from Table 1, all the five species have similar energies at their triplet (³Σ) state and quintet (⁵Σ) state. Tables 2 to 6 show the optimized geometric parameters obtained using the three DFT methods and the MP2 method with a basis set 6-311G for Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) species at their triplet (³Σ) and quintet (⁵Σ) states. The vibrational frequencies and the vibrational mode assignment of the molecules are listed in Tables 7 and 8. It's a pity that the data of Fe(CO)₅ species can't be obtained by the second-order Moller-Plesset perturbation theory (MP2) method. According to the structural classification, detailed discussions will be carried out in the following subsections.

Table 2. Optimized geometric parameters (Å, deg) at four theoretical levels with a 6-311G basis set for FeCO species at two states

State	Method	r _{Fe-C}	r _{C-O}	∠FeCO
FeCO (³ Σ)	B3LYP	1.7217	1.1552	180.00
	B3P86	1.7022	1.1548	180.00
	HF	1.6998	1.1550	180.00
	MP2	1.7666	1.1558	180.00
FeCO (⁵ Σ)	B3LYP	1.8498	1.1522	180.00
	B3P86	1.8274	1.1512	180.00
	HF	1.8342	1.1514	180.00
	MP2	1.8521	1.1553	180.00
r (Expt.)		1.7270	1.1586	

Fig. 2. Sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/particle).

FeCO species :

There are two conformers of FeCO species in the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) states in accordance with the geometric optimizations. In line with the recent experimental work, the ground state of FeCO is the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state. The two states of FeCO have similar energy, and both of them are structurally linear of $C_{\infty v}$ point group.

The three DFT and MP2 methods show good agreeable results with each other and there is a slight difference in total energy of the two states. For the ground state ($^3\Sigma$), the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are within 1.6998–1.7217 Å at DFT theoretical levels and the largest deviation is 0.022 Å (see Table 2). It is slightly smaller by 0.045–0.067 Å than that of the MP2 value (1.7666 Å), which is very close to the experimental numerical value (1.7270 Å). The optimized C–O bond lengths are within 1.1548–1.1552 Å, and they are little smaller than those of the MP2 value (1.1558 Å), which are also very close to the experimental value (1.1586 Å). Because of the best agreement among the bond length results, it is shown that the three DFT and MP2 methods are reliable and applicable here. For the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state, there is also a similar tendency. The optimized Fe–C bond lengths are 1.8274–1.8452 Å with the largest deviation of 0.025 Å, and the C–O bond lengths fall within 1.1512–1.1553 Å among the four different theoretical methods. The Fe–C bond length in the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state is obviously longer by about 0.1 Å than that of the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state (the ground state). This indicates that the combination of Fe with CO is stronger in the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state than in the

quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state. Thus, the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state is more stable.

For the ground state ($^3\Sigma$), there are two bending vibrational modes and two stretching modes. The bending modes are made the distortions of the linear molecule into a bent one by two end atoms (Fe and O) departing from the molecular axis according to two directions vertical to the molecular axis. The calculated bending vibrational frequency is 325.9 cm^{-1} at B3LYP level, the Fe–C stretching is 543.1 cm^{-1} , and the C–O stretching is 2037.1 cm^{-1} , respectively. For the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state, there are two bending vibrational modes and the value is 46.3 cm^{-1} at B3LYP level. These small bending vibrational frequencies indicate that the potential energy surface is shallow for the distortion to the bent molecule. The bending force constant is quite low and some constraints in the matrix sites may induce bending. The Fe–C stretching is 469.9 cm^{-1} , which is significantly smaller by about 70 cm^{-1} than that in the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state. Thus, the Fe–C bond in the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state is stronger than that in the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state.

Fe(CO)₂ species :

We use four theoretical methods mentioned above to optimize the molecular geometries of Fe(CO)₂ species in its triplet ($^3\Sigma$) and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) states, respectively, for studying their configuration and structure stability. Results indicate that the two states possess a linear structure ($D_{\infty h}$ point group) and a v-type structure (C_{2v} point group). The structure of quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state is more stable than that of the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state. Although they have very small difference in energy, the optimized geometric parameters are listed in Table 3, which indicate that the v-type structure is more stable than the linear one.

Table 3. Optimized geometric parameters (Å, deg) at four theoretical levels with a 6-311G basis set for Fe(CO)₂ species at two states

State	Method	$r_{\text{Fe-C}}$	$r_{\text{C-O}}$	$\angle\text{FeCO}$	$\angle\text{CFeC}$
Fe(CO) ₂ ($^3\Sigma$)	B3LYP	1.8493	1.1580	180.0000	180.0000
	B3P86	1.8320	1.1567	180.0000	180.0000
	HF	1.8364	1.1578	180.0000	180.0000
	MP2	1.8621	1.1664	180.0000	180.0000
Fe(CO) ₂ ($^5\Sigma$)	B3LYP	1.8175	1.1522	176.0868	109.5153
	B3P86	1.7959	1.1518	175.2895	106.8315
	HF	1.8005	1.1523	175.4361	106.7847
	MP2	1.8125	1.1520	177.0210	108.7684
r (Expt.)		1.7980	1.1586		

For the triplet state (${}^3\Sigma$), the data in Table 3 have shown that the angles between $\angle\text{CFeC}$ and $\angle\text{FeCO}$ are 180.0° at three DFT levels with 6-311G basis set. This molecule belongs to $D_{\infty h}$ symmetry, in which two FeCO moieties are symmetrically laid in the two sides of C_2 axis. The optimized Fe–C bond lengths fall within 1.8320–1.8493 Å, close to those of FeCO (${}^5\Sigma$). Meanwhile, the C–O bond lengths are within 1.1567–1.1664 Å, which are very close to those in FeCO (${}^3\Sigma$) (only longer by 0.005 Å). This observation indicates that the bonding character in the bicarbonyl Fe system is similar to that in the monocarbonyl Fe system.

For the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state, the key angle $\angle\text{CFeC}$ reflecting the molecular nonlinear character is 106.7847 – 109.5153° at three DFT levels with 6-311G basis set. Another very interesting bond angle is $\angle\text{FeCO}$, whose value is 176° . This molecule belongs to C_{2v} symmetry. The Fe–C bond lengths in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state are within 1.7959–1.8175 Å, close to the experimental value (1.7980 Å), which are shorter by ~ 0.035 Å than those in the triplet state (${}^3\Sigma$), and also significantly shorter by ~ 0.033 Å than those in the FeCO (${}^3\Sigma$). Meanwhile, the C–O bond length is shorter than that in the triplet state (${}^3\Sigma$), too. Comparing the Fe–C bond lengths of FeCO with those of Fe(CO) $_2$ in their ground states, the bonding energy of Fe–C is smaller in Fe(CO) $_2$ than that of FeCO. However, the C–O bonding lengths are almost the same in the two species.

Theoretically, when Fe atom combines with CO, the linear structure should be more stable because of the principle of the maximal superposition of the electronic clouds. However, for the Fe(CO) $_2$ species, the optimized geometric parameters listed in Table 3 indicate that the v-type structure is more stable than the linear one as there is a pair of nonbonding electrons in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state. Since the mutually exclusive energy of the pair of electrons is bigger than the energy of the maximal superposi-

tion of the electronic clouds, the key angle $\angle\text{CFeC}$ changes and the bond C–Fe–C bends. Then the v-type structure becomes more stable than the linear one because of the theory of valence shell electron pair repulsion (VSEPR).

Tables 7 and 8 also list ten vibrational mode frequencies obtained by using four theoretical methods for linear structures and nine vibrational mode frequencies for v-type structures. As the linear structure (${}^3\Sigma$), 2038.2 and 2149.5 cm^{-1} are assigned to two C=O character absorption peaks with symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations, while the Fe–C asymmetric stretching vibrations is 507.0 cm^{-1} . Other modes are the $\angle\text{FeCO}$ angle in-plane bending vibrational modes (447.9 and 457.0 cm^{-1}) and the C=O rock in-plane and rock out-of-plane modes (285.7 and 286.4 cm^{-1}). The remaining mode, such as 453.6 cm^{-1} , is distributed to CFeC scissors. Obviously, for the v-type structure, 1935.9 and 2045.8 cm^{-1} may be undoubtedly assigned to two C=O character absorption peaks with asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations, while 322.9 and 394.9 cm^{-1} correspond to the Fe–C asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations. These two groups of vibrational modes reflect the strengths of the corresponding bonds, respectively. Another interesting vibrational mode is 243.2 cm^{-1} , CO–CO rock out-of-plane. The remaining modes are the CFeC scissors vibrational modes (280.3 cm^{-1}) and deform mode (175.0 cm^{-1}). Furthermore, a very interesting observation is the changes of the vibrational frequencies for the C–O stretching mode. As noted in the analysis concerning geometric parameters, are in very good agreement with the data obtained by using four theoretical methods, which can also be observed.

Fe(CO) $_3$ species :

Table 4 gives the optimized geometric parameters obtained using the three DFT methods and the MP2 method with a basis set (6-311G) for Fe(CO) $_3$ species at their

Table 4. Optimized geometric parameters (Å, deg) at four theoretical levels with a 6-311G basis set for Fe(CO) $_3$ species at two states

State	Method	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^1}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^2}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^3}$	$r_{\text{C}^1\text{-O}^1}$	$r_{\text{C}^2\text{-O}^2}$	$r_{\text{C}^3\text{-O}^3}$	$\angle\text{CFeC}$
Fe(CO) $_3$ (${}^3\Sigma$)	B3LYP	1.8449	1.8453	1.8450	1.1682	1.1681	1.1681	103.3245
	B3P86	1.8073	1.8079	1.8066	1.1455	1.1453	1.1454	105.6267
	HF	1.8745	1.8744	1.8744	1.1364	1.1364	1.1364	101.8070
	MP2	1.7951	1.7951	1.7949	1.2076	1.2076	1.2077	98.4881
Fe(CO) $_3$ (${}^5\Sigma$)	B3LYP	1.8911	1.8912	1.8912	1.1454	1.1453	1.1453	111.5168
	B3P86	1.8675	1.8669	1.8681	1.1443	1.1442	1.1441	111.4579
	HF	2.0494	2.0492	2.0494	1.1306	1.1306	1.1306	111.0822
	MP2	1.8645	1.8640	1.8643	1.1692	1.1691	1.1692	107.4017

triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) and quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) states. As we can see, according to the four different theoretical levels, the two states are found to be close in energy and they have the similar structures, both of them are pyramidal structures, belonging to C_{3v} point group.

For the triplet state (${}^3\Sigma$), the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are within 1.8070–1.8745 Å at DFT theoretical levels and the largest deviation is 0.07 Å. They are slightly larger by 0.01–0.08 Å than that of the MP2 (1.7950 Å). The optimized C–O bond lengths are within 1.1364–1.1681 Å with the largest deviation of 0.03 Å, which are little smaller than those of the MP2 (1.2076 Å). The angles $\angle\text{CFeC}$ are within 101.8–105.6° at three DFT theoretical levels. They are a little larger than that of the MP2 (98.5°). For the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state, the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are 1.8675–1.8911 Å with a largest deviation of 0.024 Å, and the C–O bond lengths fall within 1.1306–1.1454 Å with a largest deviation of 0.015 Å at four different theoretical methods. The angles $\angle\text{CFeC}$ are about 111.3° at three DFT theoretical levels, and they are little larger than the MP2 value (107.4°). The Fe–C bond length in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state is obviously longer by about 0.05 Å than that of the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state. This indicates that the combination of Fe with CO is stronger in the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state than in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state. Also the $\angle\text{CFeC}$ in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state is obviously larger by about 8° than that of the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state. Thus, the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state is more stable than in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state.

Both the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state and the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ species have fifteen vibrational mode frequencies. For the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state, 1882.6, 1883.2 and 1983.9 cm^{-1} are assigned to three C=O character absorption peaks with symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations, while the Fe–CO stretching vibrations are 405.3, 446.1 and 446.7 cm^{-1} . Other modes are the C–O in-plane rocking (69.6 cm^{-1}) or out-of-plane rocking (277.4 and 282.5 cm^{-1}) vibrational modes. The remaining modes, 486.8, 487.1 and 487.4 cm^{-1} are distributed to CFeC scissors. For the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state, the C=O stretching vibrations are larger by about 150 cm^{-1} than those of the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state, they are 2031.2, 2031.87 and 2128.6 cm^{-1} , respectively. On the contrary, the Fe–C stretching vibrations are smaller by 60 cm^{-1} in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state than those of the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state. So the Fe–C bonds in

the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state are more stable than those of the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state.

Fe(CO)₄ species :

The optimized geometric parameters of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$ species at their triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) and quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) states are obtained by using the three DFT methods and the MP2 method with a basis set (6-311G) are listed in Table 5. Results show that the two states possess a square structure (D_{4h}) and a cube structure (T_d). According to the four different theoretical levels, the two structures have the similar energies.

For the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state, the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are within 1.7994–1.8378 Å, with a largest deviation of 0.04 Å. The C–O bond lengths are within 1.1663–1.1867 Å, with a largest deviation of 0.02 Å. The angles $\angle\text{CFeC}$ are all 90° using the three DFT theoretical methods and the MP2 data. This indicates that the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$ species has obviously a square (D_{4h}) symmetry structure. For the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state, the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are 2.0313–2.1263 Å with a largest deviation of 0.09 Å, and are longer by 0.14 Å than those in $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ (${}^5\Sigma$). The C–O bond length falls within 1.1388–1.1689 Å with a largest deviation of about 0.03 Å using four different theoretical methods, and they are very close to those in $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3$ (${}^5\Sigma$) (only longer by 0.008 Å). This observation indicates that the bonding character in the quartet-carbonyl Fe system is similar to that in the triplet-carbonyl Fe system. The angles $\angle\text{CFeC}$ are about 109° for the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state, and this molecule belongs to T_d point group. The Fe–C bond length in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state is significantly longer by ~ 0.25 Å than that in the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state. This indicates that the combination with Fe and CO is stronger in the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state than in the quintet (${}^5\Sigma$) state. So the triplet (${}^3\Sigma$) state with a D_{4h} symmetry structure is more stable.

We can see from Tables 7 and 8 that the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4$ species have twenty-one vibrational modes. For the D_{4h} symmetry structure (${}^3\Sigma$), 1095.3, 1917.5, 1917.5 and 2012.1 cm^{-1} are assigned to four C=O character absorption peaks with symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations, while the Fe–C symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations are 407.5 and 421.8 cm^{-1} . Other important modes are the CFeC bending or twisting vibrational modes (98.4 and 468.5 cm^{-1}) and the C=O rock in-plane and rock out-of-plane modes (181.0, 349.4, 352.8

Table 5. Optimized geometric parameters (Å, deg) at four theoretical levels with a 6-311G basis set for Fe(CO)₄ species at two states

State	Method	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^1}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^2}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^3}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^4}$	$r_{\text{C}^1\text{-O}^1}$	$r_{\text{C}^2\text{-O}^2}$	$r_{\text{C}^3\text{-O}^3}$	$r_{\text{C}^4\text{-O}^4}$	$\angle\text{CFeC}$
Fe(CO) ₄ (³ Σ)	B3LYP	1.8378	1.8378	1.8378	1.8378	1.1663	1.1663	1.1663	1.1663	90.0000
	B3P86	1.7994	1.7994	1.7994	1.7994	1.1674	1.1674	1.1674	1.1674	90.0000
	HF	2.6488	2.0185	2.6488	2.0185	1.1867	1.1867	1.1867	1.1867	90.0000
	MP2	1.8028	1.8028	1.8028	1.8028	1.1681	1.1681	1.1681	1.1681	90.0000
Fe(CO) ₄ (⁵ Σ)	B3LYP	2.1212	2.1212	1.9232	1.9232	1.1535	1.1535	1.1388	1.1388	108.0898
	B3P86	2.0313	2.0313	1.8738	1.8738	1.1689	1.1689	1.1632	1.1632	109.0916
	HF	2.3301	2.3301	2.1055	2.1055	1.1189	1.1189	1.1479	1.1479	108.1728
	MP2	2.1263	2.1263	1.9213	1.9215	1.1665	1.1665	1.1617	1.1616	109.1672

Table 6. Optimized geometric parameters (Å) at four theoretical levels with a 6-311G basis set for Fe(CO)₅ species at two states

State	Method	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^1}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^2}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^3}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^4}$	$r_{\text{Fe-C}^5}$	$r_{\text{C}^1\text{-O}^1}$	$r_{\text{C}^2\text{-O}^2}$	$r_{\text{C}^3\text{-O}^3}$	$r_{\text{C}^4\text{-O}^4}$	$r_{\text{C}^5\text{-O}^5}$
Fe(CO) ₅ (³ Σ)	B3LYP	2.0128	2.0128	2.1014	2.1014	2.1014	1.1702	1.1702	1.1680	1.1681	1.1680
	B3P86	1.9064	1.9064	2.1038	2.1038	2.1038	1.1371	1.1371	1.1702	1.1702	1.1702
	HF	2.0195	2.0195	2.0514	2.0514	2.0514	1.1652	1.1652	1.1612	1.1612	1.1612
Fe(CO) ₅ (³ Σ)	B3LYP	1.8139	1.8445	1.8445	1.8445	1.8445	1.1531	1.1681	1.1681	1.1681	1.1681
	B3P86	1.8192	1.8547	1.8547	1.8547	1.8548	1.1405	1.1415	1.1415	1.1415	1.1415
	HF	1.8103	1.8619	1.8619	1.8619	1.8619	1.1517	1.1668	1.1668	1.1668	1.1668

Table 7. Vibrational frequencies (cm⁻¹) and vibrational mode assignment for the Fe(CO)_n (n = 1-5) molecules in the ³Σ state at B3LYP level, computed using the 6-311G basis set

Species	Freq.	Assignment	Species	Freq.	Assignment
FeCO	325.9	FeCO bend in-plane	Fe(CO) ₂	87.0	OFeO bend in-plane
	325.9	FeCO bend out-of-plane		184.5	OFeO bend out-of-plane
	543.1	FeC stretch		285.7	CO rock in-plane
	2037.1	CO stretch		286.4	CO rock out-of-plane
				447.9	CO bend in-plane
				453.6	CFeC scissors
				457.0	CO bend out-of-plane
				507.0	CFeC asymmetry stretch
				2038.2	CO symmetry stretch
				2149.5	CO asymmetry stretch
Fe(CO) ₃	68.7	O ² FeO ³ scissors	Fe(CO) ₄	54.1	C ¹ FeC ³ rock out-of-plane
	69.6	C ¹ O ¹ rock in-plane			C ² FeC ⁴ rock out-of-plane
	80.8	FeO ¹ O ¹ O ³ umbrella		96.3	O ¹ O ² FeO ³ O ⁴ scissors
	277.4	C ³ O ³ rock out-of-plane		98.4	C ² FeC ⁴ bend in-plane
	282.5	C ² O ² rock out-of-plane		98.4	C ¹ FeC ³ bend in-plane
	290.3	C ¹ O ¹ + C ² O ² + C ³ O ³ rock		103.7	FeO ¹ O ² O ³ O ⁴ umbrella
	405.3	FeC stretch		181.0	CO rock out-of-plane
	446.1	FeC ² and FeC ³ asymmetry stretch		349.4	CO rock in-plane
	446.7	FeC ¹ stretch		352.8	C ² O ² + C ⁴ O ⁴ rock out-of-plane
	486.8	C ² FeC ³ scissors		353.5	C ¹ O ¹ + C ³ O ³ rock out-of-plane
	487.1	C ¹ FeC ³ scissors			
	487.4	C ¹ FeC ² scissors		407.5	FeC stretch

Table-7 (contd.)

	1882.6	C ¹ O ¹ and C ¹ O ² symmetry stretch		421.8	FeC ² and FeC ⁴ symmetry stretch
	1883.2	C ² O ¹ and C ² O ² asymmetry stretch		468.5	C ¹ FeC ³ twist
	1983.9	CO stretch		468.6	C ² FeC ⁴ twist
				544.5	C ¹ C ² FeC ³ C ⁴ scissors
				598.7	C ² FeC ⁴ scissors
				598.7	C ¹ FeC ³ scissors
				604.8	FeC ¹ C ² C ³ C ⁴ umbrella
				1905.3	C ¹ O ¹ and C ³ O ³ symmetry stretch + C ² O ² and C ⁴ O ⁴ symmetry stretch
				1917.5	C ¹ O ¹ and C ³ O ³ asymmetry stretch + C ² O ² and C ⁴ O ⁴ asymmetry stretch
				1917.5	C ¹ O ¹ and C ² O ² symmetry stretch + C ³ O ³ and C ⁴ O ⁴ symmetry stretch
				2012.1	CO stretch
Fe(CO) ₅	35.5	C ³ FeC ⁵ rock out-of-plane	Fe(CO) ₅	286.7	FeC ² and FeC ⁵ symmetry stretch + FeC ¹ stretch
		C ² FeC ⁴ rock out-of-plane			C ⁴ FeC ⁵ scissors +
	41.3	O ³ FeO ⁴ scissors		306.1	FeC ¹ rock
	45.0	C ¹ O ¹ rock			C ² FeC ⁵ scissors +
	61.1	O ⁴ FeO ⁵ scissors		307.1	FeC ¹ rock
	61.7	O ² FeO ³ scissors			FeC ¹ rock
	67.7	O ² FeO ⁵ scissors		328.0	FeC ¹ rock
	76.8	FeO ² O ³ O ⁴ O ⁵ umbrella		337.9	C ² FeC ⁵ scissors +
	147.8	C ² O ² + C ³ O ³ + C ⁴ O ⁴ + C ⁵ O ⁵ rock in-plane		400.1	C ¹ O ¹ rock
	167.5	FeC ³ and FeC ⁵ symmetry stretch + FeC ² and FeC ⁴ symmetry stretch		406.5	FeC ² C ³ C ⁴ C ⁵ umbrella
	179.7	C ² O ² + C ³ O ³ + C ⁴ O ⁴ + C ⁵ O ⁵ deform		1829.6	C ² FeC ⁴ bend + C ³ FeC ⁵ bend
	195.9	FeC ¹ + FeC ² + FeC ³ deform			C ³ O ³ and C ⁴ O ⁴ asymmetry stretch
	215.2	FeC ¹ + FeC ⁴ + FeC ⁵ deform		1843.9	C ³ O ³ and C ⁵ O ⁵ asymmetry stretch + C ² O ² and C ⁴ O ⁴
	241.6	C ³ FeC ⁴ scissors + C ¹ O ¹ rock		1855.6	asymmetry stretch
	262.6	FeC ² and FeC ⁵ symmetry stretch		1936.3	C ² O ² and C ⁵ O ⁵ asymmetry stretch
	265.8	FeC ² and FeC ⁵ asymmetry stretch			C ¹ O ¹ and C ² O ² + C ³ O ³ + C ⁴ O ⁴ + C ⁵ O ⁵ asymmetry stretch
				2010.9	C ¹ O ¹ and C ² O ² + C ³ O ³ + C ⁴ O ⁴ + C ⁵ O ⁵ symmetry stretch

Table-8 (contd.)

56.7	C ⁴ O ⁴ and C ⁵ O ⁵ rock out-of-plane	381.2	FeC ¹ and FeC ² symmetry stretch
62.8	O ³ rock out-of-plane	393.2	FeC ¹ and FeC ² asymmetry stretch
66.9	O ⁴ and O ⁵ rock out-of-plane	433.2	FeC ¹ and FeC ² asymmetry stretch +
68.2	O ¹ and O ² rock in-plane		C ³ O ³ rock
84.2	O ¹ and O ² rock out-of-plane	452.2	C ¹ FeC ² scissors
162.6	C ³ O ³ , C ⁴ O ⁴ and C ⁵ O ⁵ rock in-plane	484.5	C ¹ FeC ² bend
175.6	FeC ³ and FeC ⁵ deform	1995.8	C ³ O ³ and C ⁵ O ⁵ asymmetry stretch
188.5	FeC ⁵ stretch	2032.7	C ⁴ O ⁴ and C ⁵ O ⁵ asymmetry stretch
226.7	FeC ⁴ and FeC ⁵ deform		stretch
229.3	FeC ³ stretch	2047.0	C ¹ O ¹ and C ² O ² symmetry stretch
240.4	FeC ³ and FeC ⁴ symmetry stretch	2075.6	C ¹ O ¹ and C ² O ² asymmetry stretch
274.9	C ³ FeC ⁵ scissors		stretch
285.1	FeC ³ C ⁴ C ⁵ umbrella	2157.4	CO stretch

and 353.5 cm⁻¹). The remaining modes, 544.5 and 598.7 cm⁻¹ are distributed to CFeC scissors. For the *T_d* structure (⁵Σ), 1925.0, 2023.2, 2066.1 and 2149.9 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to four C=O character absorption peaks with asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations, while the Fe–C asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations are 368.4 and 377.3 cm⁻¹ respectively. These two groups of vibrational modes reflect the strengths of the corresponding bonds, respectively. Other vibrational modes of interest are 56.8, 59.6, 291.0 and 357.0 cm⁻¹ modes, four C=O rock in-plane or rock out-of-plane. The remaining modes are the scissors vibrational modes (44.4 and 416.8 cm⁻¹) and twist modes (72.2 and 307.7 cm⁻¹). For the triplet (³Σ) state the stretching frequencies of four C=O are significantly smaller by 100 cm⁻¹ than those of quintet (⁵Σ) state, while the Fe–C stretching frequencies are larger by about 40 cm⁻¹ than those of quintet (⁵Σ) state.

Fe(CO)₅ species :

Table 6 exhibits the optimized geometric parameters obtained using the three DFT methods with a basis set (6-311G) for Fe(CO)₅ species at their triplet (³Σ) and quintet (⁵Σ) states. According to the four different theoretical levels, the two states of Fe(CO)₅ are found to be close in energy. The triplet (³Σ) state has a *D_{3h}* structure while the quintet (⁵Σ) state has a *C_{4v}* structure.

The data shown that the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are within 1.9064–2.1038 Å at DFT theoretical levels and the largest deviation is 0.2 Å in the triplet state, and the optimized C–O bond lengths are within 1.1371–1.1702 Å with a largest deviation of 0.03 Å. For the quintet (⁵Σ) state, the optimized Fe–C bond lengths are 1.8103–1.8619 Å with a largest deviation of 0.05 Å, and the C–O bond lengths fall within 1.1405–1.1681 Å with a largest deviation of 0.02 Å at four different theoretical methods. The *C_{4v}* structure is in good agreement with other theoretical and experimental data. It is generally accepted that the theoretically most stable geometry for Fe(CO)₅ is the trigonal bipyramid (³Σ)^{49,50}. This configuration has been confirmed by X-ray diffraction⁵¹ and electron diffraction measurements^{51–54}. Nevertheless, this *D_{3h}* structure (³Σ) has slightly higher energy for Fe(CO)₅ than the square pyramidal structure *C_{4v}* (⁵Σ) (vide Table 1). The Fe–C bond length in the quintet (⁵Σ) state is obviously shorter by about 0.2 Å than that of the triplet (³Σ) state. Thus the quintet (⁵Σ) state being a *C_{4v}* square pyramidal structure is more stable.

Fe(CO)₅ has been spectroscopically investigated for decades, and the CO stretching modes of Fe(CO)₅ with *D_{3h}* (³Σ) symmetry are well-known. The corresponding vibrational frequencies and vibrational modes are displayed

in Table 7. The five C=O have asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations at 1829.6, 1845.9, 1855.6, 1936.3 and 2010.9 cm^{-1} , and the Fe-C has symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations at 167.5, 262.6, 265.8 and 286.7 cm^{-1} . Other important modes are the CFeC scissoring vibrational modes (241.6, 306.1, 307.1 and 337.9 cm^{-1}) and the five-CO rocking in- or out-of-plane (35.5, 45.0, 147.8 and 328.0 cm^{-1}). For the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state (be seen Table 8), 1995.8, 2032.7, 2047.0, 2075.6 and 2149.9 cm^{-1} are assigned to five C=O character absorption peaks with asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations, while the Fe-C asymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations are 240.4, 295.9, 381.2, 393.2 and 433.2 cm^{-1} . Other vibrational modes of interest are 21.2, 55.0, 56.7 and 162.6 cm^{-1} modes, five C=O rock in-plane or rock out-of-plane. The remaining important modes are the FeC deforming vibrational modes (175.6, 226.7 and 336.6 cm^{-1}) and the five-O rocking in- or out-of-plane (62.8, 66.9, 68.2 and 84.2 cm^{-1}), respectively. For the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state the stretching frequencies of five C=O are significantly smaller by 150 cm^{-1} than those of quintet ($^3\Sigma$) state, while the Fe-C stretching frequencies are larger by about 100 cm^{-1} than those of quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state. The results indicate that the Fe-C bonds are more stronger in the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state than those in the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state, so the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state being a C_{4v} square pyramidal structure is more stable.

Bonding energies :

The sum of electronic and zero-point energies (Hartree/particle) and the calculated bonding energies for the stable configurations are listed in Table 1. As we can see from the Table 1, the order of the sum of electronic and zero-point energies for the complexes is $\text{FeCO} > \text{Fe}(\text{CO})_2 > \text{Fe}(\text{CO})_3 > \text{Fe}(\text{CO})_4 > \text{Fe}(\text{CO})_5$. That is to say, the more CO_n combines to the central Fe, the more stable the structure is. We can find from Fig. 2 that the energies of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$) species take an accurate linear relationship for the stable configurations.

We use expression $E_2 = E - E_{\text{Fe}} - nE_1$ to calculate the bonding energies. Where E is the HF energy of the complexes, E_{Fe} is the energy of Fe atom, E_1 is the HF energy of isolated CO molecule, E_2 is the bonding energy, and n is the number of CO molecules combining to central Fe atom, respectively. The energy of one Fe-C bond is $E_3 = 1/n (E - E_{\text{Fe}} - nE_1)$ and shown in Table 1,

too. In Figs. 3 and 4, it can be seen that the bonding energy decreases with the increasing value of n , while the energy of one Fe-C bond is increased (see Figs. 3 and 4). It proved that stability is enhanced with the increase of the number of CO molecules, which is in agreement with the conclusion from the HF energy.

Fig. 3. Bonding energy (Hartree/particle).

Fig. 4. Energy of one Fe-C bond (Hartree/particle).

Conclusion :

The geometries and vibrational modes analysis of the $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$) molecules have been presented in this work, where the stable structures are considered. Four methods are used to investigate the stable structures of $\text{Fe}(\text{CO})_n$ ($n = 1-5$) species. All methods get the same conclusion, for FeCO species, the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) states are found to be close in energy, and both of

them are structurally linear of $C_{\infty v}$ point group for $Fe(CO)_2$ species, the two states (both $^3\Sigma$ and $^5\Sigma$) have linear structure and v-type structure, respectively. The more stable configuration is the v-type one. For $Fe(CO)_3$ species, the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) and quintet ($^5\Sigma$) states are obviously close in energy, and they are both pyramidal structures, belonging to C_{3v} point group. But the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state is more stable than that of the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state. For the $Fe(CO)_4$ species, the two states ($^3\Sigma$ and $^5\Sigma$) possess a square (D_{4h}) structure and a cube (T_d) structure. According to the four different theoretical levels, the two structures have the similar energies and the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state being a D_{4h} symmetry structure is more stable. For the $Fe(CO)_5$ species, the triplet ($^3\Sigma$) state has a D_{3h} structure while the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state has a C_{4v} structure. The more stable configuration is a C_{4v} square pyramidal structure at the quintet ($^5\Sigma$) state. The energies for the stable configurations of $Fe(CO)_n$ ($n = 1-5$) species take on accurate linear relationship, and the bonding energy decreases along with the increasing value of n increased, while the energy of one Fe-C bond is increasing. It indicated that the more COs combines to the central atom Fe, the more stable the structure is. All the results indicate that the bond lengths, the bond angles and the energies are reliable, and the vibrational mode analysis suggests that the mechanism is reliable, too.

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